

FUNDAMENTALS OF LINGUISTICS IN THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Students who choose Russian as their first or second foreign language are trained in four main areas. Throughout the learning process, they improve their oral and written skills. At the initial stage of education, students acquire communication skills, expand their vocabulary, learn the basics of grammar and speech patterns, and develop writing skills. The main objectives of higher education education are: communication, collaboration, problem solving and implementation. The purpose of learning a second foreign language includes independent learning of other foreign languages, understanding of various contexts and texts, joint activities with representatives of different cultures and languages, the ability to successfully communicate with representatives of other cultures and self-immersion in knowledge. To achieve these standards, a large role is assigned to the teacher of a foreign language. In this article, we will look at the main methods of teaching a foreign language.*

Keywords: *communication; educational standard; methodological issues; language material; authentic texts.*

INTRODUCTION

Studying the basics of linguistics in the context of teaching Russian as a foreign language is a key aspect of effective teaching. Linguistics plays an important role in understanding the structure of a language, its features and rules, which in turn contributes to the development of effective methods of teaching foreign languages. In this article, we will consider the basic principles of linguistics that are used in teaching Russian as a foreign language, as well as their impact on the formation of the educational process and improving the quality of education. Teaching Russian as a foreign language (RCT) is a complex and multidimensional process that requires the use of various techniques and approaches. The basics of linguistics play a key role in the development of effective teaching methods, since understanding the structural and functional aspects of language allows teachers to create optimal conditions for foreign students to learn the language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology of teaching the Russian language is based on linguistic principles, such as literacy and spelling based on phonetics, graphics and spelling; grammar teaching based on grammatical theories about parts of speech, phrases and sentences; speech skills development based on the study of vocabulary, text theory and other aspects of speech learning. Modern methods of speech development have moved from the practical to the scientific level, taking into account such areas as functional stylistics, speech culture and text theory. An important source for the methodology of teaching Russian is the concept of "developmental learning", which emphasizes the need for learning that exceeds the current level of student development. Due to the increasing emphasis on the communicative component in teaching Russian, it is important for teachers to pay attention to the following aspects: compliance with literary norms in grammar, spelling and punctuation, the development of literate writing and correct pronunciation skills, the formation of

expressiveness in speech; the study of theoretical material on grammar, phonetics and vocabulary, the formation of a system of scientific concepts in the language; acquaintance with samples of literary works through reading and grammar lessons; the development of the ability to perceive literary texts and reading skills.

PHONETICS AND PHONOLOGY

One of the first tasks in teaching the Russian language is to master its sound system. The Russian language has a specific phonetic structure, including unique sounds and accents, which can be difficult for learners. Linguistic knowledge of phonetics and phonology helps teachers:

- Explain the rules of pronunciation and accentuation.
- Develop exercises to train auditory perception and articulation.
- Identify the most difficult sounds to learn and suggest strategies for mastering them.

Work on the sections "History of the Russian language", "Phonetics", "Orthoepy", "Spelling", "Vocabulary", "Morphemes", "Word formation", "Morphology", "Syntax", "Punctuation" involves step-by-step preparation of students. To achieve the best results, it is necessary to repeat the material regularly, carry out vocabulary work, develop self-control skills and conduct control work. After studying theory and completing academic assignments, students are invited to take a test based on their level of training. It is recommended to keep rating tables. To develop students' creative abilities, it is important to give assignments that require detailed answers and text analysis.

Morphology

Studying the morphology of the Russian language is important for understanding the structure of words and their changes in different grammatical forms. The Russian language is rich in various morphological categories, such as cases, gender, number and tenses. Teachers who rely on linguistic knowledge in this field can:

- Explain in detail the rules of inflection and word formation.
- Create exercises for practicing the use of morphological forms.
- To help students master complex grammatical constructions.

Syntax

The syntax of the Russian language, which includes the rules for constructing sentences and phrases, is also an important aspect in teaching RCT. Knowledge of syntactic structures allows you to:

- Explain the word order in a sentence and the features of word matching.
- Develop exercises for the formation of correct syntactic constructions.
- To analyze proposals to improve the understanding of texts in Russian.

Lexicology

Lexicology studies the vocabulary of a language and its use. The importance of lexicology in teaching RCT is that it helps:

- Identify the most commonly used words and expressions for the initial level of education.
- Explain the meanings of polysemous words and idiomatic expressions.
- Develop thematic dictionaries and exercises to expand the vocabulary of students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When studying literary texts, special attention should be paid to linguistic analysis based on stylistics. Special attention is paid to the choice of words, their forms and syntactic constructions in coherent speech, as well as the differences between spoken and written language.

It is important to distinguish between spoken and book language, business and artistic language when analyzing, studying and using language tools in works of art and other texts.

It is important to pay special attention to the theory of literature, since students are engaged in the analysis of works of fiction, which requires a deep understanding of the theoretical aspects of literary studies and is based on the principles of creating literary works and their impact on the reader. Literary concepts such as the ideas of a work, its theme and plot, structure, genre and linguistic means are of particular importance. Only systematic and purposeful work on language material will achieve the desired results.

Russian Russian communication is a key methodological principle in the study of the Russian language: the Russian language is studied as an object of cognition and as a means of communication and development of intelligence. The communicative function of language is put in the foreground, which contributes to an in-depth understanding of language structures and the development of an effective combination of conscious and automatic use of words.

The basic principles of teaching Russian include the use of exercises, educational texts and communicative situations, taking into account the knowledge gained in the lessons of the native language. This helps students to understand the peculiarities of their language more deeply and improve their speech. For successful development of speech skills, it is important to work with adapted and authentic texts of various styles and genres, including works by Russian writers, as well as texts from various fields such as history, biology, geography, etc. This allows students to familiarize themselves with the terminology of various scientific fields. The support of educational texts and situations also contributes to the development of linguistic and socio-cultural skills. The communicative principle of learning involves knowledge of linguistic stereotypes and expressions related to real situations. In Russian language lessons, training and creative exercises should be preferred to formal ones. Grammatical phenomena are considered in the context of their use as a means of communication. This approach makes language knowledge more effective and motivated. The socio-cultural line of education is aimed at transferring knowledge about human life, society and nature through language, including history, cultural characteristics, economic problems, environmental problems and other aspects. This line is based on carefully selected texts, a list of which can be found in Russian-language programs. The main strategy is aimed at developing skills and abilities in various speech situations that promote effective communication and mutual understanding. The program is focused on using effective strategies to solve communication problems. An important role is played by training in mental and behavioral actions, such as orientation in a situation, the ability to anticipate the actions of the interlocutor, control over their behavior and a critical attitude to speech and non-speech actions. The main emphasis is on knowledge of the rules of effective communication: honesty, clarity of expression, brevity, as well as consideration of psychological aspects such as tact and tolerance.

Thus, the communicative approach to teaching the Russian language and the importance of speech practice presuppose the integration of language and speech material into the educational process. The Russian language within the framework of language education sets itself the goals of forming a linguistic culture of the individual, a conscious attitude to language as a means of communication and knowledge acquisition, as well as the development of communicative competence. In general, the main purpose of teaching the Russian language is to ensure the comprehensive development of students in the fields of language, thinking, intelligence, spirituality and aesthetics. Teaching Russian as a mother tongue and a foreign language, as well

as teaching methods of both languages, can only be coordinated through unification and mutual enrichment.

THE COMMUNICATIVE METHOD

The communicative teaching method focuses on the use of language in real communication situations. The basics of linguistics help in this approach by providing knowledge about various speech acts and language functions. Teachers can:

- Create dialogues and role-playing games that reflect real communicative situations.
- To teach students conversation skills and the use of various speech strategies.

Grammar-translation method

This method is based on the study of grammatical rules and the translation of texts.

Linguistic knowledge helps:

- Systematize grammatical material and explain its logical structure.
- Analyze and translate complex grammatical structures.
- Compare the grammatical features of the Russian language with the native language of the students.

Interactive methods

The use of modern technologies and interactive methods is also based on linguistic knowledge. The development of multimedia textbooks, online courses and language learning applications requires an understanding of linguistic principles. Teachers can:

- Integrate phonetic simulators and programs to improve pronunciation.
- Create interactive grammar exercises and vocabulary games.
- Provide feedback and correct errors in real time.

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of Russian language lessons is to form and develop linguistic, target and country competencies in their interrelationship. Therefore, it is important that the educational material has a national orientation, allowing students to understand the peculiarities of the life of Russians in comparison with the lives of residents of the country of study, which can stimulate interest in both languages. The teacher should focus on the comprehensive development of students' speech skills. The communicative-activity approach is aimed at forming the general communicative competence of students and solving problems of language competence. Personality-oriented learning begins with defining lesson goals and expected results. For each lesson to be successful, the teacher begins by explaining to the students what they will learn in the lesson and what goals they will be able to achieve after it. It is also important to define the topic of the lesson in order to take into account specific tasks and motivate students to work with clearly defined goals.

The structure of the lesson includes a mandatory start with a warm-up session, where students prepare to learn the language and the topic of the lesson. Students' basic knowledge is updated through a system of questions and exercises. While studying the educational material, students learn to solve problem situations, observe language phenomena, analyze and summarize information. The teacher encourages students to study the material independently, offering to draw their own conclusions before checking in the textbook. The selection of texts for lessons plays an important role, therefore, it is necessary to choose texts that meet educational, educational and artistic standards, as well as meet the interests and needs of students. Before starting work on texts, it is important to choose topics in accordance with the goals of the program and its socio-cultural direction. It is important to start the lesson with a system of questions before and after the text in

order to help students understand the content of the text, see how language tools are used to achieve a communicative goal, and give them the opportunity to independently apply the information they have learned. Teachers can use text-based research, search, and problem-based assignments. When choosing a language material, it is important to take into account the peculiarities of the students' language and use facts from their native language for assignments. Translations of texts, terms, grammatical terms and comparative analysis should be mandatory in the lesson.

Assignments for students should be individualized, include various forms of work (individual, group, pair), discussions, dialogues and tasks of varying complexity. Additional tasks should be provided for students with a high level of training. Homework should be adapted to different levels of students. In addition, students are encouraged to perform creative tasks, as working on them contributes to the successful development of language and speech material.

The basics of linguistics play a fundamental role in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language. Understanding the phonetic, morphological, syntactic and lexical aspects of language allows teachers to develop effective methodological approaches and create optimal conditions for successful language acquisition. The introduction of linguistic knowledge into teaching practice contributes to improving the quality of education and achieving high results in learning the Russian language by foreign students.

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